

Quest for Woman's Space Inashapurana Debi's- "Subarnalata"

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Abstract

Searching for womanhood in the society is an undying process in this world. Men dominate women due to their financial power but beyond this patriarchal system women are also dominated by their own sex but it goes unnoticed by the Society. Whereas Ashpurana Debi in her trilogy tried to expose the unexposed facets. This paper is an attempt to picturize women as a predator of women through the eyes of Debi. Thrust for women space in her family is the central idea that revolves around the novel and it is highlighted or projected through the protagonist Subarnalatha and her cruel mother-in-law Muktakeshi. She represents the life of women in late 19th century and early 20th century and fights hard in her tight corner situation to get her place in her family. Women speak of feminism together but female themselves are not ready to support for the growth of female in their family rather try to oppress them.

Keywords: Quest, identity, filial relationship

Gender studies is a field of interdisciplinary study dependable to the study of feminism, male domination and even sexuality comes together with this "women beware of women." In the society women are not only facing problems by men but also by women's search of their space is a form of their struggle. The male oriented society denying space to women is same in the side of women also. Gender studies examine how one's sex reflects one's identity in this pretentious paradise where we supposed to live as a puppet in the hands of men.

"Women must need space and money to express herself in this society through her pen"-Virginia Woolf. Feminism is politically, culturally or economically aimed to establish equal rights and legal protection for women. Elaine Showalter and Elizabeth Barret Browning were some of the feminists who voiced for the rights of women, one such writer is Ashapurana Debi. She lights out the quest for feminism in her trilogy in particular her second of three novels Subarnalatha.

This is the story of the protagonist Subarnalatha, who tries to come out from her predetermined societal setup. Most of her works are based on gender biased and the protagonists mainly spent their time in their kitchen like boiling cooker. They could not come out of their confined walls even though there is need. Thus this paper pictures

women dictatorship in own sex. Subarnalatha belonged to a middle class family and brought up as a single child. She longed to get education like her mother but both remained uneducated. It happened because of their society where women were not allowed to enlighten through education.

Subarnalatha was forcibly married at the age of 9 to the man who is twice older than her. Her marriage was carried out without her mother's wish. Being a middle class Brahmin housewife she had gone through numerous difficult times, like she was not given her own space for reading books, not to be free with her husband, etcetera. She could not voice out her voice. Subarnalatha was created as blood and flesh of women fought for her rights. When she entered into an orthodox Brahmin family she came to know that her mother-in-law (Muktakeshi) constrained all of the family members including men, she did not have a happy married life with her suspicious husband, who saw her as a machine which satisfies his physical pleasure but not a body with emotions.

In her family, they did not have rights to talk, women were voiceless. So they could open up neither their mind nor their heart to their husband. For instance they are not allowed to talk to any male in their family and also to the male visitor to their house. Muktakeshi served food for her sons and forced her daughter-in-laws to stay away from their husbands in public even inside their house. So they could not speak with each other and happened to lead an unequal family life. They are allowed to spend their time only during their night sleep in their private room hence they find little time to be happy. Subarnalatha's husband wished to spend time with her during day time without the knowledge of others. So he called her to the attic in their house but she could not go because of her burdened household work by Muktakeshi. They were treated like slaves; they have to act accordingly to the words of Muktakeshi and their husbands. They were deprived from social respect, peaceful life, and even from rest.

Muktakeshi was not ready to treat her daughter-in-law as her own daughter; this is what prevails in this modern society also. In the present scenario too such families are prevailing. Such a situation is projected through the scene when once her daughter came to her house to compensate this expense. Muktakeshi ordered her sons to drop their wives in their father's house respectively but Subarnalata fought against that and tried to remain with her husband. Since she hate her father she was forcibly dropped in one of her relatives house where she gained the help of a man to read books. It added some flame to fire where Subarnalata was suspected by her husband. And when her family planned to build a new house she pasture her husband to build their room with a balcony so that she could have a connection to the nature but when this was known to her mother-in-law she erotically scolded her. And at the end, all her tortures turned into saddest memories which was chewed by her in a new balcony house which was build by her husband to her to safe guard from the supremacy of Muktakeshi.

Thus this paper is enclosed with the writing of Roseanne Barr "THE THING WOMEN HAVE YET TO LEARN IS NOBODY GIVES YOU POWER. JUST TAKE IT." Subarnalatha no more survived in that women oppressing society and came out of it and started growing her child Bakul as an enlightened women.

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